

OS Awards

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D3.3 Visualization Tool for OS projects implementing the OS indicators – v1

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable describes the first version of the Visualization Tool for OS projects implementing the OS indicators, developed in task T3.4.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
DoA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
EOSA	European Open Source Academy
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IT	Information Technology

REST	Representational State Transfer
SFTP	SSH File Transfer Protocol
Tx.x	Task number
VT	Visualization Tool
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

This document is the first in a series of three iterations regarding the development of the Visualization Tool. Starting with a review of the state of the art, this document details, among other aspects, the architectural design, implementation, deployment, and integration of the tool.

1 Introduction

As mentioned in the DoA, the task T3.4 *“will enable identification of suitable nominees to Awards based on metrics for the identified areas per T3.1/3.2/3.3”*. This requires the development of a specific framework to enable the visualization and dynamic analysis of the critical areas and its components.

In addition, the DoA also mentions that *“the framework will also facilitate the proposals of nominees to Awards throughout the project in a single source, allowing the output of a report with recommendations at policy level for increased interest for the contribution to, integration of and exploitation of OS assets in Europe”*.

The framework to be developed receives the name of **Visualization Tool**, and it consists of a software component capable of visualizing a series of indicators and metrics obtained from different Open Source repositories and databases, and also capable of generating reports based on the input data.

The Visualization Tool is intended to be accessible to the general public, with special attention to the European Open Source Academy (EOSA) ^[1], so that the data obtained from the other WP3 tasks can be analysed and the list of nominees/winners can be determined accordingly. However, it is important to note that the Visualization Tool complies with privacy regulations, and all personal information will not be made available to the general public.

2 State of the art

As mentioned in the previous section, the objective of this task is the development of a software component capable of visualizing data from different sources. To do this, it should be noted that there are numerous tools on the market, which could be used as a starting point for development.

The most relevant existing tools are:

Grafana

Grafana ^[2] is an Open Source data observability and visualization platform designed to query, visualize, and alert on metrics, logs, and traces from systems and applications. It allows to create interactive and customizable dashboards to monitor and analyze the performance of IT infrastructure or any other type of data, unifying information from diverse data sources into a single interface.

Figure 1. Grafana sample screen ^[20].

Kibana

Kibana ^[3] is also an Open Source tool that provides a visual interface in a web browser for exploring, visualizing, and analyzing data stored in Elasticsearch. It is part of the Elastic Stack (formerly known as the ELK Stack) and allows users to create interactive dashboards with charts, maps, and tables to identify trends, anomalies, and patterns in their data in real time.

Figure 2. Kibana sample screen [21].

Apache Superset

Apache Superset [4] is a modern, intuitive, Open Source data analysis and visualization platform that allows users to explore data, create interactive dashboards, and share visualizations without advanced technical knowledge. Originally developed by Airbnb and now supported by the Apache Software Foundation, it offers a scalable and flexible solution for transforming data into actionable insights.

Figure 3. Apache Superset sample screen [22].

GrimoireLab

GrimoireLab [5] is an Open Source toolkit developed by the CHAOSS project [6] for data analysis in software development. Its purpose is to collect data from diverse sources such as code repositories, issue tracking systems, and communication tools, then organize, analyze, and present it in interactive visualizations or dashboards. This allows developers and organizations to evaluate and monitor the health of their software projects, make informed decisions, and understand the relationships between their teams and components.

Figure 4. GrimoireLab sample screen [23].

GrimoireLab includes several different modules. The following figure shows which ones have been used or are planned to be used in a later stage of the development: ElasticSearch, Kibiter and Manuscripts.

Figura 5. GrimoireLab modules [24] considered for the Visualization Tool.

However, a more manual approach to development can be taken, dispensing with the aforementioned tools. To make this task easier, there are several frameworks that greatly facilitate development. The most relevant are:

Chart.js

Chart.js ^[7] is an Open Source JavaScript library for creating interactive and engaging charts in web applications, using HTML5 Canvas rendering technology. It offers up to eight chart types (such as line, bar, and pie charts), is easy to use, small in size, responsive in the browser, and supports animation and customization.

D3.js

D3.js (Data-Driven Documents) ^[8] is a JavaScript library for creating interactive and dynamic data visualizations, using standards like SVG, HTML, and CSS to manipulate data and render it graphically.

Rescharts

Recharts ^[9] is a component-based charting library for React applications that combines the declarative philosophy of React with the visualization capabilities of D3.js to create responsive and interactive charts.

Highcharts

Highcharts ^[10] is a JavaScript library that allows to create interactive charts for websites and mobile applications. It is a powerful, versatile, and easy-to-use tool that supports a wide variety of chart types and is free for non-commercial use. It also offers specialized products such as Highcharts Stock for financial charts, Highcharts Maps for maps, and Highcharts Gantt for project visualization.

Apache ECharts

Apache ECharts ^[11] is an Open Source JavaScript data visualization library that allows to easily create interactive and customizable charts and dashboards for the web. It is a declarative framework, and is compatible with most web and mobile frameworks, can handle large data sets, and allows chart export and real-time data visualization.

ApexCharts

ApexCharts ^[12] is an Open Source JavaScript library that enables developers to create high-quality, interactive data visualizations for web applications and dashboards. It offers a wide variety of chart types (line, bar, pie, etc.), is easy to implement, customizable, and supports responsive designs, making it ideal for presenting data in an engaging and functional way.

The following table shows the comparison between the different frameworks mentioned:

	Chart.js	D3.js	Rescharts	Highcharts	ECharts	ApexCharts
License	MIT	BSD-3	MIT	Proprietary	Apache 2.0	MIT
Free	Yes	Yes	Yes	Personal use	Yes	Yes
Customizable	4/5	5/5	4/5	4/5	4/5	4/5
Easy to use	4/5	1/5	4/5	5/5	4/5	5/5

TypeScript	Yes	Low Q.	Low Q.	Yes	Yes	Yes
React	Yes	Manual	Yes	Yes	Manual	Yes
Angular	Yes	Manual	No	Yes	Manual	Yes
Vue	Yes	Manual	No	Yes	Manual	Yes
Mobile responsive	Built-in	Manual	Built-in	Built-in	Built-in	Built-in
Line chart	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Timeline chart	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Scatter chart	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Area chart	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Pie chart	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Donut chart	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Bullet chart	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
Radar chart	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Funnel chart	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Gantt chart	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
Network chart	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
Grouped bars	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Stacked bars	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Negative bars	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Discrete bars	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Horizontal bars	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3D	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Legends	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mouse over	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
onClick	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Supports SVG	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Supports Canvas	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No
GitHub Stars	62.1k	106k	21.1k	11.5k	56.7k	13.2k

GrimoireLab was selected for several reasons:

- Its modular design is well suited to the needs of the Visualization Tool, allowing to use the most appropriate modules for the task.
- It has a large community with a significant number of contributions.
- There is communication between members of the CHAOSS project and members of the Consortium. This has allowed for easy and very productive contact.

3 System Requirements analysis

For a first analysis of the system requirements, a first approach of the Visualization Tool has been deployed on a virtual machine on an OpenStack^[13] system, with the following characteristics:

RAM Memory	8 GB
Disk size	100 GB
Number of Virtual CPUs	4
Operative System	Linux Ubuntu 24.04 Server

Compute

Instances
Used 1 of 4

VCPUs
Used 4 of 4

RAM
Used 8GB of 8GB

Volume

Volumes
Used 1 of 11

Volume Snapshots
Used 0 of 10

Volume Storage
Used 100GB of 100GB

Figure 6. OpenStack set up for the Visualization Tool.

The different subcomponents of the Visualization Tool are dockerized, so the following version of Docker Engine has been installed:

Docker Engine version	28.0.0 (2025-02-19)
Disk API version	1.48
Number of Virtual CPUs	4
Operative System	Linux Ubuntu 24.04 Server

The orchestration and version control are performed by Docker Compose and GIT:

Docker Compose version	2.33.0
GIT	2.43.0

With these specifications, the Visualization Tool has been verified to run smoothly, so no significant changes to system requirements are expected for future versions.

4 Architectural design & implementation

To design the architecture of the Visualization Tool, it was decided that it would consist of a series of subcomponents, which operate with each other to satisfy the requirements of the task. These subcomponents are the following:

- **Gateway:** this subcomponent, developed in OS Awards project, allows communication between the Visualization Tool and other users or external components, exposing a REST API for the purpose of integration.
- **SFTP Server:** this subcomponent, developed in OS Awards project, acts as a Server for the files that the Visualization Tool will use to build the different dashboards.
- **Data Collector:** this subcomponent, developed in OS Awards project, is responsible for collecting the files from the previously mentioned Server and loading the information they contain into the tool.
- **GrimoireLab:** this external subcomponent consists of a CHAOSS developed toolset for software development analytics and data visualization. It includes a series of modules for different tasks, of which the Visualization Tool will use the following:
 1. **Elasticsearch:** an enriched database to store the information to be displayed.
 2. **Kibiter:** a module based on Kibana to visualize the data.
 3. **Manuscripts:** a module to generate reports.

4.1 Architectural design

To present the architecture of the Visualization Tool, it will be specified according to the C4 Model ^[14], of which the following levels will be detailed:

- System context model.
- Container model.
- Component model.

4.1.1 System context model

The System context model represents the highest level of abstraction and describes something that delivers value to its users, whether they are human or not.

Figure 7. Visualization Tool System context model.

4.1.2 Container model

According to C4 Model, a container is a piece of software that needs to be running for the overall software system to work, such as an application or a data store. Another way to express it would be that a container corresponds to a component or group of components that performs a specific task.

The container model of the Visualization Tool shows the used technologies and how containers communicate with each other:

Figure 8. Visualization Tool Container model.

Using the Gateway subcomponent as the endpoint, the Visualization Tool receives information from an Operator or from another component within OSAwards Framework. Once uploaded to the SFTP Server, the information is collected periodically by the Data Collector subcomponent, which will build the appropriate dashboard to be visualized in GrimoireLab subcomponent by an Operator.

4.1.3 Component model

According to C4 Model, a component is a grouping of related functionality encapsulated behind a well-defined interface.

Figure 9. Visualization Tool Component model.

In the case of the Visualization Tool, each container described in the previous section includes a single component, each one taking charge of fulfilling its function in the general workflow.

4.2 Implementation

The subcomponents included in the Visualization Tool run in separate Docker containers, being orchestrated with Docker Compose. The following diagram shows a first approach of the orchestration:

Figure 10. Diagram of the first approach of Docker containers orchestration.

Separating GrimoireLab into the two subcomponents (Elasticsearch^[15] and Kibiter^[16]) that the Visualization Tool includes, the second approach obtained is:

Figure 11. Diagram of the second approach of Docker containers orchestration.

Finally, the Visualization Tool also includes the following auxiliar subcomponents:

- **Reverse Proxy:** this subcomponent, based on Traefik ^[17], provides the Visualization Tool with secure communications using the HTTPS protocol, also acting as a router between the different subcomponents.
- **Portainer:** this subcomponent ^[18] provides a graphical interface for managing container environments such as Docker.

Adding these subcomponents to the diagram:

Figure 12. Final diagram of Docker containers orchestration.

All the subcomponents belong to a Docker Network to facilitate the communication between the containers. The Docker Network to be used is the one created by default (and named “**default**”). No additional network configuration is required because the different subcomponents will be able to communicate through container names.

The following section goes into detail about the implementation of the different subcomponents.

4.2.1 Gateway

Gateway subcomponent consists basically of a dockerized Python – Flask REST API to implement the only communication interface provided by the Visualization Tool.

It has two defined functions:

Function name	Hello
Description	Checks if the Gateway is online.

Method	GET
URL	/api/osawards/gateway/hello
Input parameters	-
Output values	{ "code": "200", "error": null, "message": "OS Awards Gateway Version x.x.x online!", "value": true }
Function name	Upload
Description	Allows uploading a data file to the SFTP Server subcomponent.
Method	POST
URL	/api/osawards/gateway/upload
Input parameters	<i>BODY:</i> { "destinationFileName": "commits_per_year_country.csv" } <i>ATTACHMENT:</i> Excel / CSV data file.
Output values	{ "code": "200", "error": null, "value": true }

It also includes a configuration file, to set values to the following properties:

gateway.version	The version of the Gateway subcomponent.
gateway.locale.language	The default language.
gateway.timeout	The default timeout.
gateway.sftp.host	The SFTP Server Docker container name.
gateway.sftp.port	The SFTP Server listening port.
gateway.sftp.username	The SFTP Server username.
gateway.sftp.password	The SFTP Server password for the username.
gateway.sftp.timeout	The SFTP response timeout.
gateway.sftp.directory.data	The SFTP Server directory for the data.

The next figure shows a configuration example:

```
[GATEWAY]
gateway.version = 0.1.1
gateway.locale.language = en
gateway.timeout = 5

[GATEWAY-SFTP]
gateway.sftp.host = osawards.sftp.dck
gateway.sftp.port = 2238
gateway.sftp.username = *****
gateway.sftp.password = *****
gateway.sftp.timeout = 900
gateway.sftp.directory.data = /data/
```

Figure 13. Gateway configuration file example.

To build the Docker container, Gateway includes the Dockerfile:

```
FROM python:3.9-slim-bullseye

COPY . /app
WORKDIR /app

RUN apt-get update && apt install curl iputils-ping -y && \
    pip install --upgrade pip --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt

EXPOSE 5010

ENTRYPOINT ["sh", "./init.sh"]
```

Figure 14. Gateway Dockerfile.

As the file indicates, the 5010 port is exposed as an internal port, and it uses the libraries listed in the *requirements.txt* file, whose content is:

```
elasticsearch == 8.17.2
Flask == 2.1.1
Flask-JWT-Extended == 4.4.1
jsonschema == 4.17.3
pandas == 2.2.3
paramiko == 3.5.0
requests == 2.31.0
Werkzeug == 2.2.3
```

Figure 15. Gateway dependencies.

Finally, an *init.sh* file is included to start the container. This is because in the future it may be decided to execute other terminal instructions, such as setting values to environment variables, etc.

```
#!/bin/bash

python gateway.py
```

Figure 16. Gateway *init.sh* file.

4.2.2 SFTP Server

SFTP Server subcomponent consists, as its name indicates, of a secure file server. The Visualization Tool uses this server to:

- Receive and store data files from other WP3 components.
- Provide the Data Collector subcomponent with these files for building the visualization dashboards.

SFTP Server defines the following directory structure:

Figure 17. SFTP Server directory structure.

To build the Docker container, SFTP Server includes the Dockerfile:

```
FROM alpine

# Parameters from the Dockerfile
ARG SFTP_ROOT_DIRECTORY
ARG SFTP_GROUPNAME
ARG SFTP_USERNAME
ARG SFTP_PASSWORD
ARG SFTP_UID_GID

# Install OpenSSH Server
RUN apk add --no-cache openssh
COPY ./sshd_config /etc/ssh/

# Create the default directories
RUN mkdir /osawards \
  && mkdir /osawards/data && chmod 777 /osawards/data \
  && mkdir /osawards/templates && chmod 777 /osawards/templates

# Copy the template files
COPY templates/* /osawards/templates/

# Create the Group
RUN addgroup --gid $SFTP_UID_GID $SFTP_GROUPNAME

# Create the users
RUN adduser -h $SFTP_ROOT_DIRECTORY -H -u $SFTP_UID_GID \
  -G $SFTP_GROUPNAME $SFTP_USERNAME;\
  echo $SFTP_USERNAME:$SFTP_PASSWORD | chpasswd

COPY ./entrypoint.sh /usr/bin/
RUN chmod +x /usr/bin/entrypoint.sh

EXPOSE 22

CMD ["/usr/bin/entrypoint.sh"]
```

Figure 18. SFTP Server Dockerfile.

Summarizing, the Dockerfile installs the OpenSSH Server, creates both directories (data and templates), establish a default user and password and exposes internally the port 22.

Finally, the container is started executing the *entrypoint.sh* script:

```
#!/bin/sh

# Regenerate SSH host keys if this is the first time the container is started:
INIT_FILE=/initialized
if [ ! -f "$INIT_FILE" ]; then
    echo "Generating SSH host keys..."
    ssh-keygen -A
    echo "1" > $INIT_FILE
fi

# Start the OpenSSH server:
/usr/sbin/sshd -D -e
```

Figure 19. SFTP Server entrypoint.

4.2.3 Data Collector

Data Collector consists of a Python program as a periodically executed process. Each time it runs, it performs the following steps, repeated periodically:

- Data Collector downloads the existing data and template files from the SFTP Server.
- If data files exist, and they are downloaded, Data Collector creates in Elasticsearch the necessary elements to build a complete dashboard. Those elements are:
 1. Index pattern.
 2. Visualization.
 3. Dashboard.
- The process finishes and waits for the next execution.

Data Collector includes a configuration file with the following properties:

collector.version	The version of the Data Collector subcomponent.
collector.locale.language	The default language.
collector.sftp.host	The SFTP Server Docker container name.
collector.sftp.port	The SFTP Server listening port.
collector.sftp.user	The SFTP Server username.
collector.sftp.pass	The SFTP Server password for the username.
collector.sftp.path.data	The SFTP data directory.
collector.sftp.path.templ	The SFTP Server templates directory.

The next figure shows a configuration example:

```
[COLLECTOR]
collector.version = 0.1.1
collector.locale.language = es

[SFTP]
collector.sftp.host = osawards.sftp.dck
collector.sftp.port = 2238
collector.sftp.user = *****
collector.sftp.pass = *****
collector.sftp.path.data = /data
collector.sftp.path.templ = /templates
```

Figure 20. Data Collector configuration file example.

As in the other subcomponents, Data Collector includes a Dockerfile to build the Docker container:

```
FROM python:3.10-alpine

COPY . /app
WORKDIR /app

RUN chmod 777 /app/data && \
    chmod 777 /app/templates && \
    pip install --upgrade pip --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt

CMD sh ./init.sh
```

Figure 21. Data Collector Dockerfile

Permissions for temporary directories for data and templates are changed; the dependencies are installed and its own *init.sh* file is executed as the endpoint.

The *requirements.txt* file contains the following dependencies:

```
elasticsearch == 8.17.2
pandas == 2.2.3
paramiko == 3.5.1
requests == 2.32.3
```

Figure 22. Data Collector dependencies.

And the init.sh file includes the code:

```
#!/bin/bash  
  
python datacollector.py
```

Figure 23. Data Collector init.sh file.

4.2.4 Other subcomponents

The Visualization Tool does not take part in the implementation of the remaining subcomponents: GrimoireLab, Reverse Proxy and Portainer. It only downloads their Docker images to have them available and assigns values to some of their environment variables at the time of building the containers. In this way, the subcomponents that make up the Visualization Tool could be conceptually divided into two categories:

- **Internal implementation:** Gateway, SFTP Server and Data Collector.
- **External implementation:** GrimoireLab, Reverse Proxy and Portainer.

Figure 24. Conceptual division of subcomponents of the VT based on implementation.

5 Deployment

All subcomponents of the Visualization Tool are deployed using Docker Compose. But first, it is needed to choose a target directory and download the code from the repository:

```
$ cd <VT_directory>
$ git clone <VT_repository>
```

The selected directory should display the contents:

- **osawards.datacollector.dck**: the source code of the Data Collector subcomponent.
- **osawards.gateway.dck**: the source code of the Gateway subcomponent.
- **osawards.sftp.dck**: the source code of the SFTP Server subcomponent.
- **docker-compose.yaml**: the Docker Compose configuration file.
- **README.md**: the *README* file.

Figure 25. VT content downloaded from the repository.

Note that only the code for subcomponents in the **Internal Implementation** category is downloaded.

A closer look at the Docker Compose configuration file reveals the following descriptions for each service to be deployed:

SFTP Server

The container and image name, the directory where the Dockerfile is located, the Docker network to which it is attached, and a series of server configuration arguments are defined.

```
sftp:  
  container_name: osawards.sftp.dck  
  image: osawards/sftp.dck  
  build:  
    context: osawards.sftp.dck  
    dockerfile: Dockerfile  
    args:  
      - SFTP_ROOT_DIRECTORY=/osawards  
      - SFTP_GROUPNAME=sftp  
      - SFTP_USERNAME=*****  
      - SFTP_PASSWORD=*****  
      - SFTP_UID_GID=3000  
  networks:  
    - default
```

Figure 26. Docker Compose definition for SFTP Server service.

Elasticsearch

The container and image name are defined, values are assigned to environment variables, the internal port 9200 is exposed, the volume to be used is indicated, and the Docker network to which it is attached is specified.

```
elasticsearch:  
  image: docker.elastic.co/elasticsearch/elasticsearch:7.17.10  
  container_name: osawards.elastic.dck  
  environment:  
    - discovery.type=single-node  
    - ES_JAVA_OPTS=-Xms1g -Xmx1g  
  expose:  
    - 9200  
  networks:  
    - default  
  volumes:  
    - esdata:/usr/share/elasticsearch/data
```

Figure 27. Docker Compose definition for Elasticsearch service.

Kibiter

The container and image name are defined, values are assigned to environment variables, the internal port 5601 is exposed, the Docker network to which it is attached is indicated, its dependency on Elasticsearch is specified, and finally a series of labels are added so that the Reverse Proxy detects the service.

```
kibiter:
  image: bitergia/kibiter:community-v6.8.6-3
  container_name: osawards.kibiter.dck
  environment:
    - ELASTICSEARCH_URL=http://osawards.elastic.dck:9200
    - NODE_OPTIONS=--max-old-space-size=1000
    - SERVER_NAME=kibiter
    - XPACK_GRAPH_ENABLED=false
    - XPACK_MONITORING_ENABLED=false
    - XPACK_REPORTING_ENABLED=false
    - XPACK_SECURITY_ENABLED=false
    - PROJECT_NAME=OS Awards
  expose:
    - 5601
  networks:
    - default
  depends_on:
    - elasticsearch
  labels:
    - "traefik.enable=true"
    - "traefik.http.routers.kibiter.rule=Host(`osawards.digital.tecnalia.dev`)"
    - "traefik.http.routers.kibiter.tls=true"
    - "traefik.http.routers.kibiter.entrypoints=websecure"
    - "traefik.http.routers.kibiter.tls.certresolver=myresolver"
    - "traefik.http.services.kibiter.loadbalancer.server.port=5601"
```

Figure 28. Docker Compose definition for Kibiter service.

Gateway

The container and image name are defined, as well as the directory where the Dockerfile is located, the Docker network to which it is attached is indicated, and the labels are added so that the Reverse Proxy can detect the service.

```
gateway:
  container_name: osawards.gateway.dck
  image: osawards/gateway.dck
  build:
    context: osawards.gateway.dck
    dockerfile: Dockerfile
  networks:
    - default
  labels:
    - "traefik.enable=true"
    - "traefik.http.routers.engine.rule=Host(`osawards.digital.tecnalia.dev`) && PathPrefix(`/api/osawards/gateway`)"
    - "traefik.http.routers.engine.tls=true"
    - "traefik.http.routers.engine.entrypoints=websecure"
```

Figure 29. Docker Compose definition for Gateway service.

Data Collector

The container and image name are defined, as well as the directory where the Dockerfile is located, values are assigned to environment variables, the Docker network to which it is attached is indicated, and its dependency on the Elasticsearch and Kibiter services is specified.

```
datacollector:
  image: osawards/datacollector.dck
  container_name: osawards.datacollector.dck
  build:
    context: osawards.datacollector.dck
    dockerfile: Dockerfile
  environment:
    - ELASTICSEARCH_URL=http://osawards.elastic.dck:9200
    - KIBITER_URL=http://osawards.kibiter.dck:5601
    - DATA_DIRECTORY=data
    - TEMPLATES_DIRECTORY=templates
    - WAIT_INTERVAL=21600
  networks:
    - default
  depends_on:
    - elasticsearch
    - kibiter
```

Figure 30. Docker Compose definition for Data Collector service.

Reverse Proxy

The container and image name are defined, as well as the initial commands to be executed, the secure port 443 is exposed as internal and external, the volumes to be used are defined, the Docker network to which it is attached is indicated, its dependence on the Elasticsearch, Kibiter and Gateway services is specified, and finally a series of configuration tags are added.

```
proxy:
  image: traefik:v2.10.1
  container_name: osawards.proxy.dck
  restart: always
  command:
    - "--providers.docker=true"
    - "--providers.docker.exposedbydefault=false"
    - "--entryPoints.websecure.address=:443"
    - "--entrypoints.websecure.http.tls=true"
    - "--certificatesresolvers.myresolver.acme.tlschallenge=true"
    - "--certificatesresolvers.myresolver.acme.email=alberto.molinuevo@tecnalia.com"
    - "--certificatesresolvers.myresolver.acme.storage=/letsencrypt/acme.json"
  ports:
    - 443:443
  volumes:
    - ./letsencrypt:/letsencrypt"
    - /var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock:ro"
  networks:
    - default
  depends_on:
    - elasticsearch
    - kibiter
    - gateway
  labels:
    - "traefik.enable=true"
    - "traefik.docker.network=default"
    - "traefik.http.routers.dashboard-api.rule=Host(`traefik.osawards.digital.tecnalia.dev`)"
    - "traefik.http.routers.dashboard-api.entrypoints=websecure"
    - "traefik.http.routers.dashboard-api.service=api@internal"
```

Figure 31. Docker Compose definition for Reverse Proxy service.

Portainer

The container and image name are defined, an administration password and security policies are indicated, the secure port 9443 is exposed as internal and external, the volumes to be used are defined and the Docker network to which it is attached is indicated.

```
portainer:  
  container_name: osawards.portainer.dck  
  image: portainer/portainer-ce:latest  
  restart: unless-stopped  
  command: --admin-password '$$2a$$10$$rg0qrWk7sfMmQ9.a4g.qA.0p5f551fm3WeM2v2h/AY3ejS.ttdjIe'  
  security_opt:  
    - no-new-privileges:true  
  ports:  
    - 9443:9443  
  networks:  
    - default  
  volumes:  
    - /etc/localtime:/etc/localtime:ro  
    - /var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock:ro  
    - ./volumes/portainer-data:/data
```

Figure 32. Docker Compose definition for Portainer service.

Finally, the Docker Compose file also indicates the volume to be used by Elasticsearch service:

```
volumes:  
  esdata:
```

Figure 33. Docker Compose definition for the volume used by Elasticsearch.

At this point, all that remains is to launch the deployment:

```
$ sudo docker compose up -d
```

To verify that the deployment has worked correctly, access the Portainer user interface and check that all services are up and running.

<input type="checkbox"/> Name ↓↑	State ↓↑ Filter ▾	Quick Actions	Stack ↓↑	Image ↓↑
<input type="checkbox"/> osawards.datacollector.dck	running		osawards	osawards/datacollector.dck
<input type="checkbox"/> osawards.elastic.dck	running		osawards	docker.elastic.co/elasticsearch/elasticsearch:7.17.10
<input type="checkbox"/> osawards.gateway.dck	running		osawards	osawards/gateway.dck
<input type="checkbox"/> osawards.kibiter.dck	running		osawards	bitergia/kibiter:community-v6.8.6-3
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> osawards.portainer.dck	running		osawards	portainer/portainer-ce:latest
<input type="checkbox"/> osawards.proxy.dck	running		osawards	traefik:v2.10.1
<input type="checkbox"/> osawards.sftp.dck	running		osawards	osawards/sftp.dck

Figure 34. Running containers in Portainer.

6 Integration & Communication interfaces

The Gateway subcomponent exposes its REST API to establish communication with other OSAWARDS sources (operators and other WP components).

At the current development stage, the Gateway subcomponent provides a single function to upload information files to SFTP Server. This function is part of the only communication interface defined by the Visualization Tool, and will be named **OSAWARDS_INT_01**.

The interface definition is the following:

Interface ID	OSAWARDS_INT_01
Description	Allows uploading a data file to the SFTP Server subcomponent.
Involver partners	TECNALIA
Technology	Python – Flask REST API
Type	Unidirectional
From	Task Force
To	Thematic Initiatives
URL	/api/osawards/gateway/upload
Method	POST
Input parameters	<i>BODY:</i> { "destinationFileName": "commits_per_year_country.csv" } <i>ATTACHMENT:</i> Excel / CSV data file.
Output values	{ "code": "200", "error": null, "value": true }

Figure 35. Visualization Tool communication interface.

Concerning access to the tool, it will be integrated into the EOSA website ^[1]. Collaboration between WP3, WP7, and WP8 will be necessary to ensure that the Visualization Tool carries is EOSA-branded (regarding its style and displaying). This feature is not yet available in the current development stage, but a proof of concept has indeed been carried out.

The following figures show a preliminary approach of how the Visualization Tool could be integrated with the EOSA website. A sample frontend has been developed to give an idea of this initial approach:

Figure 36. First approach of the integrated Visualization Tool (1).

Visualization Tool

Popularity per year and country

Back

Add a filter +

Figure 37. First approach of the integrated Visualization Tool (2).

7 Conclusions

Combining pre-existing software subcomponents (GrimoireLab, Reverse Proxy and Portainer) with proprietary subcomponents (Gateway, SFTP Server and Data Collector) allows the Visualization Tool to provide a degree of customization and automation tailored to the requirements of the task. Creating a visualization dashboard is reduced to a call to the Gateway subcomponent attaching the data file.

At this stage of development, a preliminary version of the Visualization Tool is deployed on the Tecnalia premises, and it is capable of generating dashboards programmatically to visualize basic indicators and metrics. That includes the creation on GrimoireLab of the three necessary elements to visualize the information provided by an indicator/metric: **index patterns, visualizations and dashboards**:

Saved Objects

[Export 3 objects](#) [Import](#) [Refresh](#)

From here you can delete saved objects, such as saved searches. You can also edit the raw data of saved objects. Typically objects are only modified via their associated application, which is probably what you should use instead of this screen.

Search...		Type	Delete	Export
<input type="checkbox"/>	Type	Title	Actions	
<input type="checkbox"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/>				

Rows per page: 20

Figure 38. Elements created on GrimoireLab for indicator/metric.

Figure 39. Indicator/metric added to GrimoireLab.

At a more advanced stage, the Visualization Tool will be able to implement more complex visualizations of indicators and metrics, thus displaying information more closely aligned with the needs it must address.

Using the sample frontend has allowed to establish the starting point for how the tool can be integrated with the EOSA website, and at least initiate a discussion to begin working on it.

Figure 40. First approach of the integrated Visualization Tool (3).

In a future step, WP3, WP7, and WP8 will collaborate to replace the sample frontend with a fully integrated and EOSA-branded version. The evolution of this development will be included in upcoming deliverables.

As a final step, the Visualization Tool will include GrimoireLab's Manuscripts ^[19] subcomponent for generating reports, once the pre-development requirements gathering prior to this specific development has been completed.

8 References

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